

Towards Improving Area Estimates and Greenhouse Gas Emissions Data for Peat under Grassland Conversion in Scotland

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Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Background	5
2. Designing and carrying out stratified sampling design for peat depth and landcover at plot and model polygon scale	7
2.1 UKGHGI intensive and extensive grassland output.....	7
2.2 Hierarchical model for selection of sites for peat depth verification.....	7
2.3 Remote Surveys.....	8
2.4 Ground surveys	8
3. Testing UKGHGI model polygon predictions of peat presence	11
3.1 Validating UKGHGI polygon predictions of grassland on peat	11
3.2 Variation in polygon size or locality.....	12
3.3 Best estimates for grassland on peat area and associated emissions	13
3.4 Sample Point Scale	14
3.5 Considering additional datasets.....	15
4. Validate and compare ground surveys with new 10m peat model	16
5. Test UKGHGI model predictions of land use cover on peatland sites	19
6. Developing approaches to identify potential historic peat/organic soil conversion to grassland	22
7. Improve GHG emissions estimates for grasslands on peat in Scotland	24
8. Modelling water table from an intensive grassland on peat site.....	27
9. Discussion.....	29
9.1 Initial Validation of Grassland on Peat	29
9.2 Difficulties Associated with Modelling Small Fragments at a National Scale.....	29
9.3 Peatland degradation, emissions and loss from organic rich soils.....	29
9.4 Change over 30 years – potential signs of deintensification of ‘grassland on peat’	30
9.5 Data cleaning approaches	31
Appendices.....	32
Appendix 1: Selection of field site photos	32
Appendix 2: Combined Grass on Peat Datasets.....	35
Appendix 3: LCM Grassland descriptions.....	38
References.....	39

Executive Summary

1. Areas of peatland conversion are currently estimated to be a large source of up to 6.34 Mt of CO₂ equivalent per year. Out of this total, conversion to intensive and extensive grassland is estimated to contribute ca 2 Mt, despite the relatively low estimated area for this land use (100kha out of 1.95mi ha peatland). Hence, the intensive and extensive grasslands areas have been considered as a potential priority for peatland restoration to reduce emissions. However, the locations and distribution of these ‘grass on peat’ sites were acknowledged to be highly uncertain in the inventory, due to difficulties in modelling peatland *per se*, and especially small areas of such land cover conversions, in a nationwide framework.
2. We conducted a systematic, Scotland-wide survey of areas predicted to be either intensive or extensive grassland on peat in the current Inventory spatial data. Sampling of sites was done according to a random, hierarchical approach to ensure even sampling of size classes, climate regions of Scotland and grassland types, which limit biases in the dataset. Within any given site, we sampled peat depth and land cover multiple times.
3. For the new dataset, we visited 124 sites and found 21 to contain peat of 50 cm or over in the majority of the randomly assigned sample points within them. Sixty-nine were found to contain peat at least somewhere within the polygon. Within the sites confirmed to contain peat, we frequently found less intensive land use than the modelled intensive or extensive grassland, with rush-dominated or other modified peatland vegetation commonly found. Although such areas would still be assigned to the overall ‘4C Grassland’ high-level Inventory reporting category¹, such land cover would be assigned to a lower emitting factor (‘Modified Bog’) in the Inventory methodology. The project supplemental datasets confirm the presence of grassland on peat but also that the detection of such small-scale features is difficult. Most sites contained organic soils which represent a significant stock of carbon, emissions from which may still be considerable.
4. While acknowledging the level of undersampling within dataset relative to the number of potential grass on peat sites, we suggest that the estimated 101,000 ha of intensive and extensive grassland on peat is an overestimate. The true value could lie within the region of 2000-24,000 ha. We reached the lower end of this estimate by multiplying the fraction of grass on peat observations within the sampled polygons by the original dataset area. The upper end was estimated by adding potential ‘false negative’ areas as generated by an estimate from an experimental 10 m digital soil map produced for the RESAS SRP CentrePeat and Land Use

¹ The individual peatland condition categories are assigned to the LULUCF land categories with the majority area falling under Grassland or Wetland (as per Figure A 3.18 in the Annex in Brown et al., 2023):

- 4A Forest Land: Forest;
- 4B Cropland: Cropland;
- 4C Grassland: Eroding Modified Bog, Modified Bog, Extensive Grassland, Intensive Grassland, Rewetted Modified Bog (from Modified Bog), Rewetted Bog or Fen (from Eroding Modified Bog, Intensive and Extensive Grassland);
- 4D Wetland: Near Natural Bog/Fen, Extracted Domestic, Extracted Industrial, Rewetted Bog or Fen (from Forest Land, Cropland, Extracted Domestic, Extracted Industrial and pre-1990 Rewetted Fen),
- 4E Settlement: Settlement

Change projects (unpublished). However, as this experimental model has some limitations, the upper estimate could be higher in reality.

5. We reviewed literature on emissions from grass on peat sites and concluded that the emissions factor could not be adjusted at this time. Therefore, we applied current emissions factor estimates for Intensive and Extensive grassland peat condition categories to the upper and lower area estimates for grass on peat coverage, concluding that emissions could be in the range of 0.037 to 0.516 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹. We found that even if polygons were not found to be intensive or extensive grassland, many had significant amounts of peat (up to 30 % of area), therefore carry emissions factors of their own, meaning that the differential between grass on peat cannot simply be subtracted from initial estimates.
6. While it is not currently feasible to produce a replacement spatial data product to that in current use for reporting due to insufficient data, the findings of this work nevertheless suggest that there is less intensive and extensive grassland on peat than currently reported and, by extension, emissions are likely to be lower overall from this type of land use on peat than the current estimate of ~ 2 Mt out of a 6.34 Mt peatland total.
7. By only testing positive predictions of grassland on peat, we can only revise its total area across Scotland downward (by subtracting negative observations), but this does not take into account areas of improved peatland that were not predicted by the model (false negatives). Using Ordnance Survey Maps from the 1800s, we have developed an approach to identify areas of former boggy vegetation that are now more intensively managed. An alternative model of peatland extent for Scotland (currently still in development as part of the SRP) also suggested a different spatial distribution, and lower overall extent, of intensive and extensive grassland on peat, and which could be tested with the same field sampling protocol as used in this report.

1. Background

An estimated 6.34 Mt CO₂ is emitted from Scottish peatlands each year, with approximately 38% of this attributed to deep peat (> 0.5 m) under conversion to extensive or intensive grassland according to the UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory (UKGHGI). The peat map in use in the current UKGHGI estimated 1.9 million ha of peat, based on a model (Evans et al. 2017, Artz et al. 2019) that incorporates information from the 1:250k Soils of Scotland, 1:25k (partial coverage) Soils of Scotland and British Geological Society UK DigiMap soil mapping (v6). In this model, any mapped polygons that contained a mix of soil types inclusive of peat after resolving 100% peat areas on the basis of matching observations in the three parent maps were allocated to the shallowest sloping ground within such mixed polygons on the basis of the observed slope threshold of 15% within the National Soil Inventory of Scotland (NSIS), which was the upper 84th percentile of where peat > 0.5 m was found to be present in a national database of soil pits. Even at the time of the Inventory compilation, it was acknowledged that this peat model is not a perfect representation of the true distribution of peat in Scotland, but it was deemed the most useful data product that could enable locating smaller peat fragments given its nominal 10 m resolution.

This mismatch between predicted peat body boundaries at local scale presents a challenge when mapping grassland on peat, as this is a land use conversion that generally occurs at the edges of former peatlands. The model training and validation data of verified peat locations available to date have also largely focused on areas where peat is still overlain with a habitat that contains elements of peatland vegetation. In the NSIS database, for example, only 3 locations on peat were sampled on ley grassland (assumed equivalent to intensive grassland) and only 25 meadow- or rush-type pastures (assumed equivalent to extensive grassland) out of 728 peat soil profiles. Similarly, the Peatland ACTION peat depth dataset, which contains nearly 100,000 point observations of peat depth across Scotland, is systematically biased against grassland conversions as this land use type was not targeted for restoration to date and has only been included in e.g., the Peatland Code as an eligible activity in spring 2023. This therefore presents an enormous challenge when trying to validate such edge habitats as the required ground validation data are extremely sparse. Against the NSIS validation data, only 1 out of the 3 validated intensive grassland on peat locations is predicted to be such in the UKGHGI 1990 base layer, and out of the 25 validated extensive grassland on peat, only 6 locations were predicted such in the UKGHGI. Similarly, when testing whether any Peatland ACTION location data exist on the UKGHGI, only 330 out of nearly 100,000 point observations were found to match the estimated grassland on peat locations. Of these 330 field validated sites, 31% of the points were found to be peat <0.5 m, i.e., false positives for peat presence, and, out of the residual locations verified to be on peat, at least 15% were found not to be grassland land cover. This suggested that an active effort is required to produce a larger, and spatially representative, database of validated grassland on peat, through field surveys.

The third limitation of the current UKGHGI is that an assumption has been made ((Evans et al. 2017) and subsequent UK National Inventory Reporting submissions) that grassland cover on peat has remained unchanged since 1990. This assumption was made on the basis that there have been no known rewetting projects on grassland. The original UKGHGI, however, used the Land Cover of Scotland 1988 (LCS88) data to derive the intensive and extensive grassland categories. In the LCS88, land cover was designated to two land cover classes wherever mosaics occurred. These were described in separate attributes for the primary land cover and secondary cover, but no indication of the relative importance of each of the two contributing classes was recorded. In the UKGHGI, an assumption had

to be made that the primary land cover co-located with peat, however this may not be a realistic assumption. In addition, a recent policy call down project to explore options for partial peatland rewetting (Artz et al. 2023) pointed to significant de-intensification of grassland conversions since the 1990s. Therefore, in this project, both the potential uncertainties in the peat mapping and the assumptions in the land cover need to be explored.

This project therefore undertook a systematic, ground-based, survey of potential grassland on peat sites as predicted by the UKGHGI model, validating both depth of peat (if any) and land cover. It then used these data to assess the validity of the current modelled extent of intensive and extensive grassland on peat in the UKGHGI 1990 baseline spatial data. In addition, these data will also be compared with the predicted extent of grassland on peat on a new, experimental, 10 m spatial resolution map of peat depth and condition (Macfarlane, Robb, Aitkenhead et al., direct submission to RESAS from the CentrePeat project).

2. Designing and carrying out stratified sampling design for peat depth and landcover at plot and model polygon scale

2.1 UKGHGI intensive and extensive grassland output

The UKGHGI grassland on peat total area is currently estimated at 110,029 ha, distributed across 65,998 polygons(areas of land). 30,404 are classified as ‘Extensive Grassland’ and 35,594 are classified as ‘Intensive Grassland’ (31,388 and 78,641 ha total area each). The vast majority of these polygons are less than 1 ha (79 %) but together only make up 7.5 % of the grassland on peat area. Considering their relatively small area within the whole potential UKGHGI grassland on peat dataset and that Peatland ACTION tends to specify a 100m grid for field verification of peat in the application process for restoration. We suggest that areas of grass on peat of less than 1 ha are not appropriate for restoration. The majority of modelled grass on peat area falls within 4 and 50 ha per land parcel (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Cumulative grassland on peat area across all modelled polygons.

2.2 Hierarchical model for selection of sites for peat depth verification

We used the UKGHGI modelled peat condition map for Scotland. It was our intention to identify and survey potential ‘false negative’ where grass on peat was present but not accounted for in the UKGHGI model. However, our judgement was to allocate all the field resources to testing for ‘true and false positive’ predictions given that the UKGHGI given the short timescale of the (to be achieved during

November 2023 - April 2024) and the fact that the UKGHGI was already inclusive of potential small pockets of peat within mixed soil polygons. Prior to analysis we ‘dissolved’ any intensive or extensive grassland polygons with the same classification that shared a border (this was an artefact of the LCS88 data that the model is based on). From the 54,540 ‘dissolved’ polygons, we removed all polygons <0.1ha (these contributed <1% of total area (582 ha) because they were likely artifacts of the model and/or most likely not restorable in a cost-effective manner, so were deemed not worth travelling to. We ran a random hierarchical model on the remaining 20,483 polygons according to the following hierarchy:

1. Three Met Office climate regions of Scotland (North, East and West) (Fig. 2)
2. Size class: More or less than 4ha (threshold was increased from 1ha to gain a sampling regime that was more inclusive of a range of sizes)
3. UKGHGI Land use type: Intensive or Extensive Grassland

Within the above hierarchy, 25 polygons were ‘randomly’ selected in each permutation of factors (with selection probability proportionate to their size, otherwise only tiny polygons would be selected, missing the large, very important ones), yielding a potential 300 polygon selections to assess on the ground. However, due to the deliberate biasing of the selection towards larger polygons, some of the largest were selected for sampling more than once, meaning that the total pool was reduced to 295 polygons for assessment. Within each polygon, survey points at which peat depth and land cover classification were to be assessed were randomly selected. To account (in part) for proportional sampling per size class of polygon, seven points were selected for polygons between 0-4 ha, 11 points were selected for polygons between 4-20 ha and 15 points were selected for polygons over 20 ha. The double sampling of some polygons due to the deliberate biasing of the model towards larger polygons and their large contribution to the total UKGHGI grassland condition class, meant that a small number were sampled 22 (2x the sampling for 4-20 ha polygons) or 30 (2x the sampling for 20+ ha polygons) times. This approach is scalable across polygon/site sizes as it allocates more sampling to larger size classes of polygons to ensure similar sampling effort per ha of land, the exact density of sampling can be user-specified. This sampling is well suited to polygons of different shapes, from slivers to rounder areas because of the random sampling within the shape, something that a gridded approach may not capture well. Of course, due to the randomness of the sampling there maybe undersampled areas.

We initially proposed to use polygon’s perimeter²: area ratio as a measure of shape (i.e. long, thin slivers vs rounder polygons) but when we came to this, it was clear that high perimeter²: area polygons were in fact complex polygons that did not represent the ‘slivers’ we anticipated.

2.3 Remote Surveys

Using satellite imagery, we remotely checked the selected survey polygons. Some model polygons were in fact residential, roads or forestry and it was not deemed necessary to visit those sites to measure peat depth with the constraints of the project. However, we were confident to mark the survey points within the polygons as ‘surveyed’ for landcover. 40 of the 295 polygons we randomly selected were remotely classified as residential, roads or forestry (total of 338 sample points). This is likely due to afforestation of grasslands over the past decades since the production of LCS88, the land cover map that is used in the UKGHGI peatland map. This left 255 polygons for which we attempted to acquire landowner permissions to survey the soil and land cover.

2.4 Ground surveys

Landowner permissions were acquired, and polygons were visited, for 124 out of the intended 255 polygon sites across Scotland. Within these sites, we sampled peat depth and made a land cover

assessment (according to landcover key in Evans et al. (2017)) at a total 1404 points. We defined organic horizon (peat) depth by soil auger sampling and soil surveyor assessment of texture and colour and classified a soil as 'organic' if it had an organic horizon that was equal to or more than 10 cm (definition of Histic or Folic horizon (World Reference Base for Soil Resources²)). This is a significantly more accurate approach to quantifying peat depth up to 100 cm than standard methods peat rod methods deployed by Peatland ACTION due the likelihood of overestimates by the latter when they push through soft, non-peat soil. However, due to the 100 cm length of the auger, we could not quantify peat depths of more than 100cm. A series of example photos of visited sites are shown in Appendix 1.

We were not able to obtain access to some sites but for some of these, the whole polygon (often a field) was observable from the road. Under these circumstances we classified land cover but not peat depth. There are 272 extra points distributed across 25 extra polygons where land use was recorded on the ground but not peat depth, making a total 1676 sampling points for land cover assessment.

The breakdown of sampling polygons sites where we have both peat depth and land cover classification according to the original sampling design has been relatively balanced and is as follows: UKGHGI modelled extensive grassland: 57, Intensive grassland: 67, East, North and West climate regions 39, 39 and 49 respectively. More or less than 4 ha, 68 and 56 respectively. The distribution of sampled sites across the country is shown in Fig. 2. We were not able to ground survey potential 'false negative' sites due to prioritisation of surveys of pre-cited intensive or extensively managed grassland sites on peat under difficult working conditions (short winter days and bad weather). However, we are developing a tool to identify potential areas of former rough/boggy vegetation (from c1850 OS maps) which could potentially be deployed nationwide (see section 6). Due to the random generation of polygons selected to survey evenly distributed across climate regions of Scotland, this dataset provides some balance to geographical biases associated with Peatland ACTION surveys.

² <https://www.isric.org/explore/wrb>

Figure 2: Ground (peat depths and land cover) and remote (land cover only) sample locations from the project across three climate regions of Scotland.

3. Testing UKGHGI model polygon predictions of peat presence

3.1 Validating UKGHGI polygon predictions of grassland on peat

Of the 124 UKGHGI grassland on peat polygons surveyed for peat presence (classed as 50 cm or over), only 21 were found to have contain peat in the majority of the randomly assigned sample points. However, 69 (55%) of the polygons were found to contain peat at least one sample point. 95 (76 %) of the polygons were found to contain organic soil at least at one sample point, indicating that these polygons are generally capturing organic-rich soils. Within each of the 149 polygons verified for landcover, 71 (47.7 %) had a most often ground-assessed land cover classification of Intensive Grassland or Extensive Grassland and 104 (70 %) contained at least one sampling site that was grassland.

Of the 21 polygons where the majority of sampled points were found to be peat over 50 cm (that is not to say that the majority of the polygon was peat), there was a mix of most often observed condition classes (Fig. 3). The classification of condition classes in Figure 3 are the most observed class on the ground (most polygons contained a mixture of vegetation types). Of these 21 peatland-dominated polygons, the most often observed were found to be Rush or *Molinia*-dominated. Three polygons with majority peat samples within them also had most often observed grassland-classified landcover within them. However, although ‘extensive grassland’ was the mode (most often observed) class, there were many other observed condition classes within the polygons, underlined how spatially heterogeneous some of the polygons are.

Figure 3: Counts of polygons with most often observed condition classes at sites where the majority of sampled peat depths were found to be more than 50 cm.

Sixty-nine sampled polygons were found to contain at least one sampling point where peat over 50 cm was measured. Of these sites, the majority were extensive grassland but there were also significant number of polygons that were classified in the field as ‘Rush dominated’, ‘*Molinia*’ and ‘Other modified

peatland’- all conditions associated with lower intensity management, falling within ‘Modified Bog’ in the GHG inventory (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Counts of polygons with most often observed condition classes at sites where at least one sampled peat depth was found to be more than 50 cm.

3.2 Variation in polygon size or locality

All three polygons where the majority of samples points contained peat over 50 cm and the most observed land use classed as intensive or extensive grassland were located in the Eastern Met Office climate region (Cleish Hills, Fife (0.4 ha), Southern Grampians, Angus (19.9 ha) and North Moray Coast (10.1 ha). These three sites share little in common as they are a mixture of high and low elevation, different polygon areas and different localities. The one thing they have in common is that they were all classified on the ground as ‘Extensive grassland’. However, many more positive confirmations of grass on peat are required before we identify trends/predictors of where and why they occur.

The three polygons with peat over 50 cm and grassland as their most common observations were not enough to generate quantitative spatial uncertainties of where grass on peat was present. However, we did investigate whether there the size of polygon, whether it was predicted to be intensive or extensive grassland and the climate region it was found it is related to the proportion of observations where peat was observed using a generalised linear model (GLM). There was no relationship between polygon size and proportion of peat observations with them ($P = 0.56$) but there was a significant relationship with the climate region the polygons were located in ($P = 0.001$) and the UKGHGI modelled condition class. The Eastern region had the highest median proportion of peat within polygons and sites modelled to be extensive grassland had a higher proportion of peat in samples within them (Appendix Fig.3). Within climate regions, polygons within the Forth catchment and North East Scotland had a higher proportion of peat observed within them.

3.3 Best estimates for grassland on peat area and associated emissions

After removing all polygons < 0.1 ha We sampled 124 out of over 20,000 polygons, and within each polygon, 7 to 30 locations were sampled depending on polygon area and the number of times the model selected the polygon. A statistically valid correction to the UKGHGI spatial data is not feasible due to undersampling (Section 3.2), however, the results were so stark that an initial estimate could be proposed.

For the sampled intensive grasslands as per UKGHGI (67 polygons), the average proportion of peat points in the sampled areas was 18.0%. For extensive grasslands (57), this was 28.3%. Within these polygons, the average proportion of sampling points where both grassland (either intensive or extensive) and peat was observed was 2.13 % (+/- 1.63 (95 % Confidence Interval) for extensive grasslands and 4.68 (+/- 2.7 (95 % CI)) % for intensive grasslands. There was no statistically significant effect of the area of the sampled polygons on the proportion of peat in the 'grasslands on peat' as per UKGHGI therefore a lower-end realistic peat area could be estimated based on the proportion of grassland (both intensive and extensive) peat observed within the measured polygons. To reach a lower end estimate we applied the lower 95 % CI of percentage peat (2.02 % for Intensive Grassland and 0.5 % for Extensive Grassland) to the UKGHGI modelled areas after subtracting any polygons of <0.1 ha (78,641 and 31,388 for Intensive and Extensive Grassland respectively) to reach an estimate of 1,580 ha of intensive grassland on peat and 156 ha of extensive grassland.

The area estimates above do not consider potential grassland on peat areas that are not currently accounted for in the UKGHGI model. For an upper estimate of grass on peat cover, we need to consider potential 'false negative' areas. For this, we extracted outputs of intensive and extensive grassland on peat from a model that is currently in development for the RESAS SRP (JHI-C3-1 Milestone 20 and Centrepeat) that assessed the maximum peat cover possible in Scotland by combining a wide range of land use datasets (including IACS, LCM, LCS88, NVC, NFI) and multiple peat extent models for a 'maximum likely' peat cover and condition map. We subtracted the 101k ha UKGHGI intensive and extensive grassland areas from this map to identify areas that may have been missed by the UKGHGI. This yielded 16,463 ha of potential extra (and unverified) intensive grassland on peat and 555 ha of extra intensive grassland on peat. An upper estimate of intensive grassland on peat can very tentatively (given the new mapping tools are in development and subject to large error) be estimated as the sum of the upper confidence interval estimate (5741 ha for intensive grassland and 1165 ha for extensive grassland) and the potential maximum 'false negatives' at 22,204 ha of Intensive grassland on peat and 1,720 ha of extensive grassland on peat. The results from these calculations are summarised in Table 1).

Together, we suggest a range of ~1700 ha (lower estimate) to 24,000 ha (including potential false negatives) of grassland on peat in Scotland that would carry emission factors of 15-22 t CO₂e ha⁻² yr⁻¹. We concluded (Section 7) that the emissions factors for intensive and extensive grasslands do not need to be changed at this time, therefore emissions from Intensive grassland and extensive grassland may be in the range of 0.035-0.488 and 0.002 and 0.027 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹ respectively. The estimated residual former area from the 'grassland on peat' component of the UKGHGI is likely to be either modified bog (2.5-3.3 t CO₂e ha⁻² yr⁻¹, depending on drainage) or a mixture of other organic soil types/mineral soils, which fall into a different reporting category in the Inventory.

Table 1: Estimates of area and from Intensive and Extensive Grassland on Peat

UKGHGI Condition Class	Units	UKGHGI area ha	After removing areas <0.1ha ha	Peat %	Grass and Peat %	LowerPeat and Grass %	Upper Grass and Peat %	Lower grass on peat estimate ha	False Negative area ha	Lower Limit ha	Upper limit ha
Intensive grassland		78641	78222	15.96	4.68	2.02	7.34	1580	16463	1580	22204
Extensive grassland		31388	30978	28.64	2.13	0.50	3.76	156	555	156	1720

Figure 5: Distribution of peat depths in land areas modelled in the UKGHGI to be intensive or extensive grasslands. Colours indicate the CEH landcover classification as recorded on the ground. Peat depths of over 100 cm were set at 101cm for visualisation.

3.4 Sample Point Scale

Of the 1404 sample locations where we were able to measure peat depth, distributed across 124 sites/sampled polygons, 306 (21.8 %), distributed across 69 sites, had peat that was over 50 cm in depth (Fig. 5). A higher proportion of modelled extensive grassland sites (28.6 %) were located on peat with over 50 cm than sites modelled as intensive grassland (16%). Across all sampling points, 35.6% contained were organic soils (organic horizon of at least 10 cm, as assessed by colour and texture in the field).

Of the 306 points we were able to verify peat presence over 50 cm, land cover at in the field, seven (2.3 %) were found to be intensive grassland and 37 (12.1 %) were found to be extensive grassland. The major condition classes observed on peat soils at the sample point scale were 'Other modified peatland (24.8%), 'Rush dominated' (18 %), *Molinia* (17.3 %) and 'Sedge dominated' (12.4 %) (Fig. 5).

3.5 Considering additional datasets

We combined the present peat depth and land cover dataset with 329 more data points across 23 sites collected within the framework of the UNC-F3.5 “Grassland emissions on peat” programme (2022-27). These data had considerable overlap with UKGHGI intensive or extensive grassland (133 out of 329 point observations) and as with the main survey, included a range of peat depths from 0 to over 100 cm. 196 observations were taken in areas that were not modelled to be intensive or extensive grassland by the UKGHGI model. Within the points modelled to be grassland on peat, 37 (27 %) had peat depths of over 50 cm and 71 (53 %) were classed as organic soils. Of those points found to have deep peat present, 19 were found to be grassland condition classes (14 % of all points modelled to be grassland on peat).

The UNC dataset also included a number of points that were not modelled to be grassland. Notably, 24 of the 196 non-modelled grassland on peat sites were in fact found to contain both deep peat and grassland. We were not able to conduct a systematic survey of such ‘false negative’ grassland on peat sites but these data would suggest that they do exist. All points that were found to be grassland on peat but not modelled as such were nearby modelled grass on peat polygons, again suggesting that the current model used for UK reporting is good but not perfect in its accuracy of predicted peat presence/absence. In addition to the UNC dataset, we intersected modelled intensive or extensively managed grassland with Peatland ACTION point samples of peat depth. This dataset did not have enough information on land cover to apply a UKGHGI condition class but it did add 511 more observations across 69 more sites. Due to the fact that Peatland ACTION surveys are not designed to fit within modelled UKGHGI polygons, there is a lot of variation in sampling intensity between sites. This said, the Peatland ACTION dataset shows that 356 points (69 %) contained peat. It should be stressed that this dataset is heavily biased towards sites with deep peat because Peatland ACTION officers visit where landowners believe peat to be present and where obvious features such as drainage ditches occur. In other words, these are sites that officers are actively looking for peat compared to our work where we have been directly by a randomly selected polygon to test the model. The combined current peat depths and land cover assessments for the current dataset, UNC and Peatland ACTION are presented in Appendix 2.

4. Validate and compare ground surveys with new 10m peat model

For every sample point we had peat depth data for, we extracted the modelled peat depth from a new 10m resolution model (still in development as part of the RESAS Centrepeat project). For display purposes we converted every modelled peat depth over 100 cm to 101 cm, as we did for the measured data (due to length of the auger) (Fig. 6). The updated peat mapping work achieves national-scale soil property mapping at 10 m resolution, a level of detail not previously attempted in Scotland. The ultimate aim of this work is to facilitate carbon stock estimation from soil properties (carbon concentration, bulk density) at multiple depths to help inform planning and policy. A modelling-based approach informed by both field measurement, remote sensing imagery and other spatial covariates has the potential to fill the gaps in field-based accounts, providing contiguous estimates of soil carbon content, bulk density, profile depth, organic layer thickness and peat extent. Carbon content, bulk density and profile depth were predicted using machine learning techniques trained using the Scottish Soil Database, yielding R^2 scores of 0.78, 0.65 and 0.7 respectively. Presence of peat was determined by the thickness of the organic layer for every grid cell profile (30% carbon content) that was greater or equal to 50 cm.

Figure 6: Histograms of modelled (top) and measured (bottom) peat depth at 1404 points sampled within polygons estimated to be intensive or extensive grassland on peat by the UKGHGI model.

We compared predictions of peat presence (50 cm or over) by the new 10 m model at the pixel level with measured peat depth at corresponding sample points (Fig. 6). From this, we were able to construct a confusion matrix which divides data into true and false positives and negatives (Table 2).

From the matrix we were able to measure the following to test the performance of the new 10 m model:

- Recall: What fraction of the peat soils measured to be 50 cm or deeper were predicted by the model?
- Precision: What fraction of predicted peat soils over 50 cm were actually measured to be over 50 cm?
- Accuracy: What fraction of positive and negative predictions were predicted accurately?
- Matthews Correlation Coefficient: a measure of agreement between predicted and measured peat presence (0-1) with higher values indicating better performance of the model.

Due to the fact that we were only measuring within UKGHGI-predicted peat polygons, we were not able to measure recall or accuracy for this model and therefore not able to directly compare the models' performance. However, we able to compare precision of the models within the dataset we acquired. At the fine scale of prediction of peat over 50 cm by the 10 m model and measured peat depth at point locations, the model has high accuracy, successfully predicting the absence of peat. However, this value is drawn down by the fact that the model misses peat presence, as reflected by a low recall score. The model has higher precision than the UKGHGI model due to a higher ratio of successful predictions of peat within the dataset. It must be stressed that this dataset is biased in that it only reflects points that are predicted to be peat within the UKGHGI, a non-biased validation of both datasets with data randomly sampled from across Scotland would provide a balanced comparison of the two models. The relationship between modelled and predicted peat depth at the 1404 points are visualised at Appendix 2.

Table 2 Confusion matrix for predicted and measured peat presence at 1404 UKGHGI-predicted grassland on peat sample points across the study

		MEASURED PRESENCE		STATISTICS	10M MODEL	UKGHGI
		Peat	No peat			
MODELLED PRESENCE	Peat	39	25	Recall	0.13	
	No peat	267	1073	Precision	0.61	0.22
	Peat			Accuracy	0.79	
	No peat			Matthews correlation coefficient	0.21	

We then compared the 10m model performance at the UKGHGI polygon scale by asking whether mode (most common) modelled peat depth of the 10 m pixels within the 124 surveyed UKGHGI grassland polygons was over 50 cm or not and how this compared to the mode observation of peat depth over or under 50 cm. Results from this confusion matrix are shown in Table 3. We then compared predictions of presence of peat over 50 cm in depth anywhere in the UKGHGI polygon with observations of peat presence of anywhere in the polygon in Table 4. This shows us that we can be reasonably confident in results from the 10 m model when it predicts peat under grassland, and significantly more so than where a similar prediction is made using the peatland map underpinning the current UKGHGi. However the 10 m model also has a high rate of false negatives, meaning total areas of grassland on peat may actually be underestimated. As the measured data set is based on the current GHGi mapping, comparison of recall between models is not currently possible.

Table 3 Confusion matrix for predicted and measured majority peat presence within 124 sample polygons across the study

	MEASURED MAJORITY		STATISTICS	10M MODEL	UKGHGI	
	Peat	No peat				
MODELLED MAJORITY	Peat	2	1	Recall	0.09	
	Peat	2	1	Precision	0.67	0.18
	No Peat	20	101	Accuracy	0.83	
	No Peat	20	101	Mattews correlation coefficient	0.20	

Table 4 Confusion matrix for predicted and measured peat presence at least one point within 124 sample polygons across the study

	MEASURED PRESENCE		STATISTICS	10M MODEL	UKGHGI	
	Peat	No peat				
MODELLED PRESENCE	Peat	21	3	Recall	0.30	
	Peat	21	3	Precision	0.88	0.56
	No Peat	48	52	Accuracy	0.59	
	No Peat	48	52	Mattews correlation coefficient	0.31	

5. Test UKGHGI model predictions of land use cover on peatland sites

Of the UKGHGI grassland polygons where the majority of sampled cores were over 50 cm or where there was at least one core within the polygon that had at least 50 cm of peat, we compared the observed ground survey most observed landcover with outputs from the UKCEH Land Cover Map 2020 (LCM (Morton et al. 2021)). The LCM is a 10 m rasterised landcover classification system applied to the United Kingdom. It used a combination of Sentinel 2 satellite imagery, automated algorithms and a random forest model to classify surface reflectance data into land uses (Morton et al. 2021). The LCM dataset was compared to the mode ground verification of land cover as an independent measure (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Demonstration of 10 m LCM2020 tiles overlaid on two UKGHGI grassland on peat polygons, left where the mode LCM tile is 'Improved grassland' (light green) and right, where mode LCM tile is 'Coniferous Woodland' (dark green).

For the polygons found to contain at least some peat, we classified the most common 10 m LCM tile (statistical mode tile) within that polygon. For an example of the LCM tiles within UKGHGI polygons, see Figure 7. This approach allows us to assess the whole polygon at a scale that is not possible using ground surveys (assessing the vegetation cover in the 1-3 m in front of the field staff member). We repeated this process for polygons where peat was the majority observation within the surveyed polygon (Fig. 8) then for polygons where peat was observed at least once (Fig. 9). We performed these additional assessments to test the current assumption in the UK Inventory submissions that grassland on peat has not materially changed since 1990 (the spatial data tested here refer to the 1990 baseline).

Figure 8: (A) Counts of polygons where peat over 50 cm was the majority observation in the field classified by the most common land cover observation within them, according to the UKCEH peatland land cover key. (B) Counts of the same polygons classified by the most common modelled LCM class tile within them.

Figure 9: (A) Counts of polygons where peat over 50 cm was observed at least once in the field classified by the most common land cover observation within them, according to the UKCEH peatland land cover key. (B) Counts of the same polygons classified by the most common modelled LCM class tile within them.

For grassland polygons with the majority surveyed peat depths measured to be over 50 cm, the LCM indicated that the most common class was grassland in the form of ‘Improved grassland’ (Fig. 8). This LCM class is identified as having ‘higher productivity than seminatural grasslands and lack of winter senescence’ (Appendix 3). Other peat-rich polygons were dominated by ‘acid grassland’ and ‘heather

grassland', both with significant amounts of grassland cover (Appendix 3). The other major LCM classification of these polygons was 'Bog' which corresponds to ground observations of 'Other modified bog', '*Molinia*' and 'Sedge-dominated' peatlands. This exercise indicates that many LCM tiles modelled to be 'Improved grassland' incorporates a range of vegetation based on their spectral signature, such as 'rush dominated'- a condition that is associated with lower intensity than seeded and fertilised grasslands. .

Polygons where peat soil of more than 50 cm depth was observed at least once (69 sites) followed a similar pattern to the majority peat polygons with regards to LCM classifications. The majority were classified as dominated by 'Improved grassland', 'acid grassland' and 'heather grassland' (Fig. 9).

As a final exercise, we queried the Land cover of Scotland subdominant classifications of UKGHI intensive and extensive grassland polygons larger than 0.1 ha. The majority of polygons had no secondary classification (68 %) but 10 % of polygons had a secondary classification of 'Smooth grass/rushes' and 6 % had a secondary classification of '*Nardus/Molinia*'. Given that the LCS is over 30 years old, it is plausible that polygons with significant secondary classifications such as rushes are now dominated by rushes or *Molinia*, therefore contributing to ground observations of such.

Overall, the above observations on land cover on validated UKGHGI "grassland on peat" areas with at least some peat > 50 cm suggest that they are frequently covered with vegetation types that would classify as lower emitting land cover in the UKGHGI emission factor assessments (e.g. modified bog).

6. Developing approaches to identify potential historic peat/organic soil conversion to grassland

We are investigating the feasibility of digitising peat soils from first Edition OS Six Inch to the mile maps from the 1860s using a machine learning-based approach to search for potential peat or organic soils that may have been converted to more intense grassland use (Fig. 10). Historic mapping of peat presence was performed using the “rough pasture and bog” classification present in the Ordnance Survey, Six-inch to the mile, 1st edition - 1843-1882 (<https://maps.nls.uk/os/>). These map sheets were downloaded using the MapReader pipeline (Hosseini et al. 2022) in python which allowed for simple download and tiling operations to be carried out, producing a set of 2048x2048 tiles for each map. 13 map sheets, or 624 tiles, in the area surrounding Peterhead were selected as training data, corresponding to roughly 807 km². These tiles were annotated using the CVAT platform (<https://www.cvat.ai/>) hosted on the JHI HPC cluster. This area was selected given the presence of multiple isolated raised bogs as well as a heavy historic and active agricultural presence in the area with a view of identifying areas of encroaching managed grasslands on historic peat soil.

With these annotations, a UNet segmentation architecture (Ronneberger et al. 2015) was trained to correctly identify and delineate this rough pasture and bog class. The annotated dataset was split into training, validation, and testing subsets with a roughly 75%/15%/10% split. This was performed to ensure the produced model could generalise to unseen data prior to performing inference across a wider area. Additionally, these images were augmented using the Albumentations (Buslaev et al. 2020) library to produce additional training examples. The model achieved an F1 score of 0.9926 on the training data and 0.9791 on the validation set indicating a high degree of accuracy and was then deployed to a further 44 map sheets (or 1440 individual 2048 x 2048 tiles) covering an area of roughly 1677 km², an example of this inference on unseen data is shown below. In total, according to the predictions made from the historic maps, roughly 128 km² or 7.5% of the area consisted of rough pasture. These predictions can be compared to modern GIS layers to identify areas of potentially peat soil beneath the current land use classification.

Using this approach and a concerted research effort, we could potentially predict across Scotland where areas of rough pastures/peaty soils may have been over 100 years ago. This could be used to focus our efforts on finding areas with high organic soil content, intensive land current land use and therefore potentially high emissions rates.

Figure 10: Example predictions centred at OS 382000, 859425 a) NLS OS Six Inch first ed. (Available online: <https://maps.nls.uk/view/74425309>) b) NLS OS Six Inch first ed. with overlaid prediction of the historical extent of rough pasture and bog predictions (green), c) Google Maps Imagery d) Google Maps Imagery with overlaid prediction of the historical extent of rough pasture and bog (green), e) UKGHGI baseline peat condition map and f) UKGHGI modelled grassland on peat areas.

7. Improve GHG emissions estimates for grasslands on peat in Scotland

The current UK Inventory submission (Brown et al. 2023) use the emission factors updated in early 2023 for the purposes of aligning the UKGHGI and the Peatland Code (Evans et al. 2022). For grassland on peat, these currently used on-site gaseous emission factors are extracted in Table 5. In addition, several other pathways of losses of greenhouse gas emissions are added at Tier 1, and methane and nitrous oxide emissions are converted using AR5 conversion factors for global warming potentials. The resulting total emission factor, which uses the mean on each individual EF, is shown in Table 6, i.e. the emission factors do not propagate the considerable uncertainties in individual component EFs.

Table 5. Emission factors for grassland on peat in the current UKGHGI

Category	Mean Tier 2 EF	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Sites (plots)
Carbon dioxide (t CO₂ ha⁻¹ y⁻¹)				
Intensive Grassland	14.87	11.07	18.68	11 (19)
Extensive Grassland	11.78	4.98	18.58	9 (31)
Methane (kg CH₄ ha⁻¹ y⁻¹)				
Intensive Grassland	29.03	-9.33	67.38	11 (54)
Extensive Grassland	35.91	2.24	69.58	15 (40)
Nitrous oxide (kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ y⁻¹)				
Intensive Grassland	7.39	4.09	10.69	12 (54)
Extensive Grassland	1.85	-0.3	3.95	15 (40)

Table 6. (reproduced from Evans et al. (2022)) Combined emission factors for all GHG source/sink pathways for grassland on peat categories, expressed in t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ based on IPCC AR5 100-year Global Warming Potentials (28 for CH₄ and 265 for N₂O). Emission factors based on IPCC Tier 1 defaults are shown in red. See also information above regarding the derivation of individual emission factors. Direct CH₄ EF corrected for (1-fraction of ditches) (see Equation 2.6, (IPCC 2014)).

Category	Direct CO ₂	CO ₂ from DOC	CO ₂ from POC	Direct CH ₄	CH ₄ from ditches	Direct N ₂ O	Total
Intensive Grassland	14.87	1.14	0.51	0.77	1.63	3.08	22.00
Extensive Grassland	11.78	1.14	0.51	0.96	0.74	0.76	15.88

A literature search was conducted for new publications from grassland sites on peat that would generate improved emission factors. The current UKGHGI peatland emission factor database (v18e) was last updated in December 2022 (Curator Rebekka Artz, JHI), with publications up to that month. For this project, we included a one-year overlap into our search for publications, which was limited to Web of Science, and used the following search strings for maximum potential data: grass* AND peat* AND carbon dioxide OR methane OR nitrous oxide. Table 7 shows the results of the database searches, and the number of new publications that were obtained as a result. The majority of search results included either papers that did not report primary data, were already included in the database (i.e. published in the overlap search year), were model outputs, or were duplicated from earlier searches (i.e. publications that reported carbon dioxide, methane and/or nitrous oxide fluxes).

Table 7. Results of literature searches

Emissions type	Total search results	Retained from scanning title & abstract	Total retained for inclusion in database
Carbon dioxide	48	24	3
Methane	37	10	0
Nitrous oxide	25	11	2

At the present time, the data from the resulting publications have been integrated into a research-only branch (v 18g) of the UKGHGI peatland emissions database. From the geographical location of the source data combined with a preliminary conversion of the mean reported values against the currently implemented suite of emission factors, it is evident that these are unlikely to result in recommendations that these be reviewed. The distribution of the new datasets is predominantly from highly drained sites in continental Europe, with only one site in Ireland that might be comparable in management intensity to the UK/Scottish scenarios (Fig 11). This last site, however, is described as *Trichophorum cespitosum* (deergrass) and *Erica tetralix* (heather)-dominated and as such might not be suitable for inclusion in the extensive grassland category. Visual inspection of the reported site location on aerial image data also suggested that this site is more likely to be modified bog rather than grassland conversion as per the UK Inventory classification. The other, continental European sites, all have emissions that fall in line with, or are higher than, the current confidence intervals for the present EF suite. In all cases, the management intensity, e.g. number of grass cuts, is higher than would be the equivalent use in UK/Scottish settings. A recent analysis of the two existing sites in Ireland that contribute to the UK Tier 2 EFs for grassland on peat suggested that emissions may be lower in such less managed systems (Aitova et al. 2023), however, for the purposes of the UK Tier 2 development, separate EFs can only be calculated if there are more than four separate monitoring sites contributing to a revised figure. Hence, the two new monitoring sites in Scotland (funded under the UNC project on grassland emissions from peat, 2022-2027) will be instrumental in the future production of grassland on peat EFs that are more suitable to less intensively managed grasslands in wetter UK settings such as in parts of Ireland and Scotland.

Figure 11: Map of existing (circles) and new (triangles) sites included in the intensive (yellow) and extensive (green) grassland categories within the UK peatland emissions database. Peatland extent as per the Global Peatland Map 2.0 is shown in brown for reference. There are two current monitoring locations on grassland on peat (in Aberdeenshire and Stirling areas, funded by RESAS UNC-F3.5 Grassland emissions on peat, 2022-2027) which do not yet have annual emissions estimates and so cannot yet be included.

8. Modelling water table from an intensive grassland on peat site

As an initial effort to estimate GHG emissions from an intensively managed grassland where we have a short dataset of water table depth (Fig. 12), we modelled water table depth over the year of 2023 (Fig. 13) using synthetic aperture radar backscatter from Sentinel-1 and various Sentinel-2 derived indices (Toca et al. 2023). Although the method has not been verified for wide-ranging use, we have had good success in reproducing observed water table dynamics in the Flow Country. At this site the modelled annual water level (-1.08 m) is below the average peat depth for the site (0.75 m). We therefore take 0.75m as the effective annual water table depth of the peat at this site. The value from this site is significantly higher than the implied water table depths for the UKGHGI Tier 2 EFs (Extensive grassland implied mean WTDe = 36.8 cm; Intensive grassland implied mean WTDe = 43.2 cm). It must also be stated, however, that the water table depth model has not yet been validated for heavily drained peatlands and the observed water table values for the site (from the flux tower) have not yet been QC'ed. The second limitation of remote sensing-based estimates of emissions is that it cannot model the biomass offtake component, only the water level dynamics. Although the water level relationship with net ecosystem productivity includes biomass offtake, this relationship was derived largely from sites where biomass offtake constituted a large proportion of the annual emissions and may not be applicable to Scottish farming practices which tend to have lower livestock densities and/or shorter grazing periods than Southern English or continental European locations. Ongoing monitoring on the site shown here, and another less intensively grazed site, are reported in the Underpinning National Capacity project on Grassland emissions from peat (UNC-F3.5, 2022-2027).

Figure 12: Measured water table depth at an intensive grassland on peat site in Aberdeenshire. Data shown have not yet been QCed and could be subject to change.

Figure 13: Modelled mean monthly water table depth at an intensive grassland on peat site in Aberdeenshire

9. Discussion

9.1 Initial Validation of Grassland on Peat

This study was the first directed test of the intensive and extensive grassland condition classes within the UKGHGI. It was anticipated that validation of such conditions would be variable given that the model is developed for nationwide peatland coverage (Artz et al. 2019) and the grassland polygons are often only a few hectares (Fig. 1). The initial validation of UKGHGI grassland on peat using randomised selection of polygons suggests a far more limited area, or a very different distribution, than initially estimated. However, the majority of UKGHGI “grass on peat” polygons do contain organic soils and the majority of those are indicative of grassland vegetation/condition. Twenty one of the 124 sites surveyed for peat depth and vegetation cover were found to have contain a majority peat (over 50 cm, of the samples taken), and within them three were found to contain most common observations of intensive or extensive grassland. Sixty nine of the 124 polygons sampled were found to have peat over 50 cm in depth at least one location within the polygon. When taking into account the additional UNC Grasslands and Peatland ACTION datasets, we can clearly see that grassland on peat does exist in Scotland but as yet, more work is required to determine its precise coverage.

9.2 Difficulties Associated with Modelling Small Fragments at a National Scale

Modelled exact peat presence/absence in a fragmented landscape at national scale is a challenge. At national scale, the UKGHGI model predicts peat presence with 80 % accuracy (Artz et al. 2019) but this included large parcels of peatland, potentially over 100s of hectares each with clear peatland vegetation (such as blanket bog). In contrast, grassland on peat is in its nature fragmented and marginal with small polygons of peat overlaid with non-peatland species. The early work (e.g. 1:250k soils maps) used field-based surveys that made a degree of assumptions of the underlying soils based on what the surveyors found to be the predominant vegetation in soil pits. They would have likely under-sampled grassland on peat that way if the grassland areas were fragments of a larger vegetation/peat polygon. The second issue is that the UKGHGI model then relies on these reconnaissance data if peat was a minority part of the soil unit, it was spatially allocated to the flattest ground within the polygon. Significantly more field verification of vegetation cover and soil properties at targeted potential grassland on peat sites is required to better characterise the cover of these condition classes. Additionally, the potential of grassland on peat outside of the UKGHGI predictions needs to be assessed. We have developed an approach (section 6) to identify former rough ground or boggy sites from OS maps constructed in the 1800s. A test for ‘false negative’ UKGHGI grassland on peat could be to survey for peat under contemporary grasslands that were marked as boggy vegetation in the 1800s. This proved to be beyond the resources of the current project.

9.3 Peatland degradation, emissions and loss from organic rich soils

Low observations of grassland on peat could be explained in part by the age of the data/maps that the UKGHGI peatland model, which provides the 1990 baseline for UK reporting, is based on. The peat extent model component used the various field-survey-based soil maps available for Scotland, namely the 1:250k and 1:25k soil maps in combination with the BGS map. All three of these are based on some form of spatial extrapolation of field observations that were made decades ago. With regards to land cover, the LCS88 remains the best Scotland-wide map of land cover for fine scale features that do not exist in the UKCEH Land Cover Maps, such as peat extraction and presence of erosion features, but it is now over 30 years old. This means that differences that contemporary surveys find with soil maps

may be exacerbated by the time since the survey. The discrepancy between baseline soil mapping may be particularly pronounced for peat soils that are particularly degraded, like intensive and extensive grassland. It is well documented that in agricultural peatlands in Southeast England (Dawson et al. 2010) the Netherlands (Hoogland et al. 2012), Southeast Asia (Evans et al. 2019) and Norway (Grønlund et al. 2008) that cultivated or improved and drained peatlands can lose a number of centimetres of peat per year through oxidation and structural failings. These subsidence rates are commensurate with the high GHG emissions factors that are associated with them. In addition to the challenges of mapping peat per se, it is plausible that a significant number of the intensive or extensively managed grassland on peat polygons with the UKGHGI have lost peat depth to a point where they are not classified as peat (50 cm). Indeed, we observe a wide range of peat depths from 0-100 cm, each of which could be losing soil carbon stock and have a net GHG emission similar to known grassland on peat sites, until the carbon inputs from grass match the losses from microbial metabolism.

In 2021 Baggaley et al. (2021) conducted a literature review on carbon storage and exchange in upland habitats, with a focus on organomineral soils. They found very little information on net fluxes of carbon from these soils with the only study identified showing that regularly burnt upland dry heaths can vary from being a source of $34 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ to a sink of $146 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ ($+1.2$ to $-5.3 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (Farage et al. 2009). The authors found no data to suggest the GHG balance of wet heath or upland grassland systems, therefore they could not conclude with any certainty as to whether upland organomineral systems are sources or sinks for GHGs. The authors cite (Quin et al. 2015) in the report but not in the context of GHG exchange. We highlight that this paper showed both *Nardus* and *Calluna*-dominated upland systems were measured to be net sinks for CO_2 although the dataset of chamber-based flux measurements was small and the study did not take biomass offtake by sheep grazing into account, which may have been sufficient to turn the measured net sink into a neutral or net emitting site.

We repeated the search terms from Baggaley et al. (2021) in Web of Science to update this literature search to present day. The search for papers since 2020 yielded 757 papers of which two partially informed the question of net emissions from organomineral soils in Scotland and the UK (although others had relevance to soil carbon and management). Gatis et al. (2020) measured ecosystem GHG exchange on a degraded *Molinia* bog in SW England where peat depths were less than 50 cm, however, the authors did not model annual budgets (likely due to insufficient data) so limited inference can be taken for our purposes. Li et al. (2023) measured net CO_2 exchange across a 25-year chronosequence of *Calluna* heathland development, post disturbance (through cutting). They found the system to be a net sink for CO_2 but the strength of the sink depended on the life stage of the vegetation- a variable that needs to be taken into account in the UK where burning uplands is prevalent. This paper was published from a site in the Netherlands, so further reinforces the urgent need to characterize GHG balance of systems in Scotland given differences in land management, history and climate. We currently have little information to compare GHG emissions from organic soils (organic horizon of more than 10 cm) with those from peatlands, and this remains a pressing research priority.

9.4 Change over 30 years – potential signs of deintensification of ‘grassland on peat’

Notwithstanding the accuracy of the peat extent predictions, in our field surveys we observed a significant number of plots within sites modelled to be intensive grassland and significant number of plots in modelled extensive grassland polygons that were dominated by lower intensity grazing land, including rush-dominated bog. This could suggest de-intensification since the LCS88 was prepared. A recent call down study to Scottish Government (KUC_F1.9, (Artz et al. 2023)) examined the IACS claims on UKGHGI ‘grassland on peat’ polygons and concluded similarly that a significant proportion of these areas may be covered with vegetation in lower emitting classes. Indeed, remote sensing using google earth imagery showed a doubling of soft and hard rush frequency over a 13 year period in a grazed

marginal upland area of England (Ashby et al. 2020). A number of factors could cause increases in rushes and decreases in vegetation associated with productivity, including reduction in drainage and the number and diversity of livestock on the land (Ashby et al. 2020). We need to improve our understanding of deintensification because management decisions resulting in reduction of grazing can have wide-ranging impacts on ecosystem function, and in turn GHG exchange/emissions from the soil and/or peat. As it stands, the UKGHGI model still operates on assuming no change in grassland use on peat since the 1990 baseline, and hence a renewed assessment of current land use and land use change is important in this regard.

9.5 Data cleaning approaches

We originally aimed to develop a data cleaning approach for the intensive and extensively managed areas of the UKGHGI but due to low observed frequency of such areas there is not enough data to derive any predictive relationships in order to confidently exclude any major polygons. As part of our site selection process we removed any polygons that were under 0.1 ha. These totalled 32,538 polygons but only 818 ha of land, leaving 109,212 ha of intensive and extensive grassland in the UKGHGI map. Additionally, we can currently recommend removing areas within a 50 m radius of any points where no peat was observed (in accordance with Peatland Code guidelines), unless there is a point within 50 m of the 'no peat' point. By doing this, the count of intensive and extensive grassland on peat area is reduced 668 ha, an approximate reduction of 13 Kt of CO₂e from the baseline emissions.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Selection of field site photos

Site on Shetland where peat had been cut and vegetation had changed to grassland

Verification of peat presence using a soil auger

Sampling a potential site in Stirlingshire

Grassland (foreground) and *Molinia* dominated bog (background) in Stirlingshire

Large grassland site with high variation in peat depth.

Appendix 2: Combined Grass on Peat Datasets

Appendix Figure 1: Distribution of peat depths collated from the current study, the UNC grasslands project and Peatland ACTION data in land areas modelled in the UKGHGI to be intensive grasslands, extensive grasslands, or not grassland on peat. Colours indicate the CEH landcover classification as recorded on the ground. Peat depths of over 100 cm were set at 101cm for visualisation.

Appendix Figure 2: Correspondence between modelled peat depth by the new 10 m model and measured peat depth. Note that although the model predicts some points to be deeper than 100 cm, they were assigned at 101 cm in order to relate to the measured depths where the maximum possible depth measurable by the auger was 100 cm. Data are deliberative 'jittered' in order to show overlapping points.

Appendix Figure 3: The percentage of points verified to have more than 50 cm peat depth within UKGHGI intensive and extensive grassland polygons. Boxes indicate the interquartile range (IQR), the central line represents the median, the line shows the 75th percentile+ 1.5*IQR and any outliers beyond the line.

Appendix 3: LCM Grassland descriptions (Taken from Morton et al. (2021))

Improved Grassland	Improved grassland is distinguished from semi-natural grasslands based on its higher productivity, lack of winter senescence, location and/or context. Grasslands lie on a continuum, so some confusion with other grassland types is inevitable. Confusion with grass-like crops will also occur.
Neutral Grassland	The UK BAP Broad Habitat <i>Neutral Grassland</i> is expected to be challenging for satellite-based classification. BAP <i>Neutral Grassland</i> is defined by botanical composition and includes semi-improved grasslands managed for silage, hay or pasture (Jackson, 2000). There is not generally an obvious spectral difference between these and other productive grass types. However, the inclusion of Context Rasters for slope and distance to rivers appear to have helped greatly with Neutral Grassland detection.
Calcareous Grassland	Calcareous Grassland class is mapped spectrally. However, the inclusion of ancillary layers for slope is expected to improve results. UKCEH does not have free access to a highly resolved soil PH/soil type layer, which we would expect to help further. For regions know to contain substantial coverage of Calcareous Grassland, for example Limestone Dales of Derbyshire and North Yorkshire, the South Downs and Salisbury Plain our results match expectations.
Acid Grassland	<p>The UK BAP <i>Acid Grassland</i> can be spectrally variable, depending on dominant species composition. Deciduous Acid grassland, dominated by <i>Molinia caerulea</i> has a distinct signal from acid grasslands dominated by mixtures other grasses, rushes, mosses, herbs and sedges. In other work we have been able to refine this class successfully. However, we did not make this separation in historical maps, so we are not able to retrieve suitable observations from Bootstrap Training.</p> <p>Bracken has a very distinctive spectral signal, but only at certain times of the year when its foliage begins to dominate its grassland understory. Historically, with restricted availability of satellite images we could not reliably separate the UK BAP <i>Bracken</i> class from <i>Acid Grassland</i> so we combined these into a single UKCEH Land Cover Class. With the greater image frequency and therefore better access to seasonal signals it may now be possible to overcome this historic limitation, but to do this we will need novel training data as we will not be able to retrieve a signal from Bootstrap Training.</p>
Heather; and Heather grassland	<p>For LCM2007 we refined the BAP <i>Dwarf Shrub and Heath</i> into two classes, depending on the density of Heather, producing the UKCEH Heather and Heather grassland classes (it is heather when there is greater than 25 % Heather Cover). This was to retain some consistency between the LCM1990 and LCM2000 classes Open Shrub Heath and Dense Shrub Heath. In some parts of the UK, significant areas of low-lying non-heather shrubs occur. For example, Gorse can form a dominant shrub layer.</p> <p>Note: the Land Cover Maps typically show confusion over Heather, Heather grassland and Bog. However, they are often difficult to separate in the field. It is</p>

	challenging to accurately estimate coverage above and below the defining threshold.
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